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Work Environment and work Engagement of Employees of the Catholic Colleges in the Ilocos Region, Philippines

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Abstract. The study wanted to determine the effect of the work environment on the work engagement of the employees. To provide a comprehensive view on the topic and established the theories of the study, related literature was reviewed. To gather the data, questionnaires were used. The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design. Weighted mean and Pearson r correlation was used to analyse the data. The study found that the bureaucratic environment is high, while, humanistic and entrepreneurial environment is moderate. In terms of work engagement, it is found that employees' work engagement is high. Concerning the correlation between work environment and work engagement, both are significantly correlated. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Keywords. Work environment, work engagement, bureaucratic, humanistic, entrepreneurial

I. Introduction

Motivating employees to perform well in their job is not a simple solution. Company performance is not isolated from employees' performance and performance is associated with the work engagement of employees. It is a truth that works disengagement has been contributing factors in decreasing work output or productivity (Pech & Slade, 2006). Thus, the management must determine factors that influence the work engagement of employees. However, giving a single solution to the problem does not solve the problem. Simply raising their salaries and benefits does not necessarily translate into a better performance and work engagement as Crowley (2017) pointed out. Harvard Business Review had published a study on the correlation between money/salaries and job satisfaction and the study found that the correlation between the two variables is very weak (Chamorro-Premuzic, 2013). It suggests that looking into other elements that promote better work engagement is important so that employers can see other factors that are influential dimensions in promoting work engagement.

Working engagement can be affected by many factors such as organizational trust, internal communication, work-life balance, and rewards (Hong, et.al. 2014). Mansoor and Hassan (2016) conducted a similar study on the factors affecting work engagement and they identified five elements that affect work engagement and these are communication, teamwork and collaboration, job role, company management, and learning and development. Othman, et.al. (2019) pointed out three factors that affect work engagement and these are leadership, compensation, and organizational culture. Abun, et.al. (2020) in their study on the employees' treatment and work engagement found that respecting workers' rights, respect in the workplace, and caring relationship significantly correlated to the employees' work engagement. However, Abun, et.al. (2020) in their study on corporate transparency practices such as involvement in decision making and information sharing does not correlate to the work engagement of employees. Pech and Slade (2006) pointed out external environment (insecurity and instability), psychological (lack of meaningfulness, lack of identification, lack of trust, sense of being undervalued, frustrated ambitions, perceived inequities, disinterested, stress, and anxiety), organizational (restructuring, inadequate conditions, poor management and leadership, ponderous bureaucracy, poor resourcing, acceptance and tolerance of low outputs, work complexity), and other (substance abuse, competency issues, laziness, illness, and interpersonal issues) affect the work engagement.

The above studies are pointing out one single factor that causes work engagement which is the working environment. The working environment encompasses many aspects of workplace issues as mentioned by different studies. But two factors that have been pointed out in the previous studies that affect work engagement are leadership and management. Leadership and management styles always affect the workplace environment. The workplace environment falls under three major classifications of workplace environments which are bureaucratic, humanistic environment, and entrepreneurial. In other words, the workplace environment can be marked by rules, procedures, centralization (bureaucratic), marked by human-oriented management which focuses on human needs and values (humanistic) and marked by entrepreneurial spirit such as autonomy, freedom, and risk-taking (entrepreneurship). There have been no studies measuring those three kinds of environment and their effect on work engagement. Thus, the current study is pursuing these factors because the three factors of the environment can contribute to work engagement. The current study would like to investigate the working environment particularly bureaucratic, humanistic, and entrepreneurial working environment and their effect on work engagement.

The study is divided into five parts and the first part is the introduction. It discusses the rationale or background of the study. The second part is the review of the related literature which discusses the different theories of the study based on the previous literature similar to the current study. The third part is the research methodology that presents the research design, locale of the study, population of the study, data gathering procedures, data gathering instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is empirical data and analysis. This part presents the data gathered through research questionnaires in different tables and followed by the analysis. The fifth part is the result and discussion and conclusion.

II. Literature Review

The literature review is a summary view of the previous books and researches presented by different authors and researchers related to the current topic. These previous ideas support the theoretical foundation of the current undertaking (Machi & McEvoy, 2016, Bloomsburg

University, n.d)). In line with this concept, this part discusses theories of the study which are supported by the previous related literature and studies.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework
Bureaucratic Environment

To understand the bureaucratic environment, one needs to understand the meaning of the word before one examines its practices. Cambridge Dictionary defines bureaucracy as a "system for controlling or managing a country, company, or organization that is operated by a large number of officials employed to follow rules carefully". This definition identifies the prime concern of bureaucracy which is to follow the rules. Similar to this definition is the definition that is offered by LEXICO (n.d), Oxford powered dictionary as it defines bureaucracy as "excessively complicated procedures" or "a system of government in which most of the important decisions are taken by state officials rather than by elected representative". This definition identifies another characteristic of bureaucracy which is the centralization of decision making. Rockman (n.d) simply describes bureaucracy as "defined complexity, division of labour, permanence, professional management, hierarchical coordination and control, strict chain of command, and legal authority". This definition capture another important feature of bureaucracy which is structure, hierarchical coordination, and obedience to authority. These definitions are enough to capture the substance of a bureaucratic environment. It is not difficult to understand the meaning of bureaucracy because it is all around us in every organization.

Weber came out with bureaucratic management theory because of the context of that time. In his assessment, the world is already increasingly rationalized. The world and its problems are getting complex and therefore decisions are no longer operated by the rule of thumbs as Taylor criticized but it should involve a rational calculation in solving daily human problems and by using rational calculation, a human can control or limit the environmental uncertainty (Touraine, 1988; Clegg, 1990). In other words, bureaucratic management is a new method for rationalizing the decision – making. There are four principles of rationality according to Weber (Brubaker, 1984; Habermas, 1984; Kalberg, 1980; Levine, 1981) and these are practical rationality, theoretical rationality, substantive rationality, and formal rationality. In a simple explanation, practical rationality involves looking for practical ways to achieve practical ends. This process still involves rational calculation because they have to analyze the problem and calculate the possible means and choose the best alternative solution to achieve the end and take action according to what they have analyzed, calculated, and planned. According to Levine (1981), all human beings engage in practical rationality when they are trying to solve their daily problems. In short, practical rationality involves immediate action to solve daily problems calculated by reason. Besides practical rationality, the second component of rationality is theoretical rationality. It involves "an increasingly theoretical mastery of reality employing increasingly precise and abstract concepts" (Weber, 1958, p. 293, cited by Ritzer, 2013, p.42). In other words, a man tries to use his reason to reflect on reality and give meaning to what is happening in the world. It is a cognitive process to know and understand reality by giving meaning to what is happening that appears haphazard (Kalberg, 1980). The third principle of rationality is substantive rationality. This refers to the values that people use in their daily life to guide their behaviour, their decisions, and their choice to choose the means to an end. The values are only rational if they are connected to the values of the actor or the moral agent (Ritzer, 2013, p.42). In other words, substantive rationality involves using one's values to guide his/her behaviour and decision making. The fourth principle of rationality is formal rationality. It is a way of thinking of choosing the means that people adopt to reach their desired

ends. People are no longer convinced with the traditional methods of doing things and they try to find the most efficient way of solving problems and achieving the ends (Kockerham, 2015). It concerns the rational calculation of choosing the means to achieve the ends which are based on the universally accepted rules, regulations, and laws (Kalberg, 1980). Thus, this formal rationality finds its place in the bureaucracy, modern law, and capitalist economy (Ritzer, 2013, p.42). In formal rationality, one cannot just choose his/her means to achieve the ends based on her/his own choice but one has to follow the structure, the rules, and the laws. Under formal rationality, the actor does not have the freedom to choose his/her means to attain the objectives. The ends or the objectives should be attained by following the structures, rules, regulations which have been established by the organization.

A bureaucratic environment refers to the concept of formal rationality. Formal rationality finds its place in the bureaucratic system of governance which is marked by rules, laws, procedures, and centralization of decision making. The purpose of the rules, regulations, procedures, and centralization of decision making is to enable the organization to control and direct all activities of the organization toward achieving its ends. All functions are structured in the hierarchical form and one can only exercise his/her functions based on prescribed functions given to him/her. There are rules and procedures to be followed which means that there are rules of inclusion and exclusion (Wagner, 1997) or there are rules of dos and don'ts. The individuals are given specific job descriptions to be followed and they can only do things within their job description and outside of the job description is not allowed. By following the rules, regulations, procedures, and authority, the actions are controlled, and therefore reducing the uncertainty or ambivalence and ensuring the attainment of goals (Wagner, 1997). To summarize it in a specific manner, Ferreira, (2004), Guzmán, (2015), Florian, (2018), Faria & Meneghetti, (2011), Ang, (2016), Pollitt, (2008), Branco, (2016), Aron, (1994) as cited by Serpa and Ferreira (2019) identified bureaucratic and rational organization in several dimensions such as functions are defined by law (formalized written rules and regulations), divisions of work with high specialization and the standardization of functions to perform, hierarchy of authority (observance of legitimate order), assessment and selection of employees based on their technical competence, formal social relationship according to the position held, employees' regular wage(standardization of wages), separation of ownership and the employee's function, and regular career of employees overtime.

On one hand, bureaucratic management practices ensure consistency, stability, and the attainment of the organizational goal. It was considered as the best tool to promote efficiency and productivity as mentioned by Armandi and Mills (1985). Besides promoting efficiency and productivity, it was also a way of controlling corruption. Check and balance must be in place to avoid dishonesty and patronage system (Frederickson et al., 2003). Thus bureaucratic management was based on the principle of control or check and balance (Considine & Lewis, 2003, p. 133) Because of its success, bureaucratic practices have been promoted and spread to private sectors including the Catholic Church. However, on the other hand, it has been criticized as the main culprit of slowing the speed of service to the customers. It focuses too much on the rules, procedures causing the delay to serve the customers (Howard, (2012), Dwyer, (2009), Kersten, (2002), AmericanCatholic.org, (2013), Martin, (2010). Besides undermining the importance of speed in service, bureaucracy is also accused of personalization of relationships and ignores informal relationships among workers (Hall, 1963). It is a form of dehumanization because the employees have no choice except to follow rules, regulations blindly (Bodley, 2002). It promotes a practice of "business as usual" because employees are always repeating doing the same job in the same way as yesterday and tomorrow and detach from their humanity, emotion, and society (Hummel, 2007). In other words, under bureaucratic management

practices, humans become machines. It is not wrong if Kang (2005) sees bureaucracy as a burden to employees or people and consequently, instead of promoting efficiency and rationality, it promotes inefficiency and irrationality (Merton, 1952).

In short, a bureaucratic environment is always characterized by routineness, rules, procedures, centralization of decision making, obedience to the authority, structures of decision making, and elimination of personal relationships ((Merton, 1957). Within this environment, one is not free to do his work according to what he/she knows best but he/she has to follow the existing job description given to him/her as a guide (Langer, et.al. 2019).

Humanistic Environment

To understand the humanistic environment, one needs to understand the meaning of the words humanism and humanistic. According to Merriam – Webster Dictionary, humanism is a "doctrine, attitude, or way of life centred on human interest or values". In short, it is a system of thought that places the most importance on human beings and his/her needs and values rather than the supernatural matter. Concerning management, it is a management style that focuses more on human needs and values ((McLeod, 2020), rather than rules, procedures, regulations, and obedience to the authority to achieve the organizational objectives like bureaucratic management does (Friedrich, 1990, Finer, 1941, Simon, 1947). While the humanistic word is an adjective and it is derived from humanism and it simply means "treating people with respect and making certain that they are safe, happy and healthy" (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d). Humanistic management then stresses respecting the dignity of human beings and looking for ways how to make them feel good and happy (Adaui & Habisch, 2013).

Basing on the definitions presented above, now one has the idea of what a humanistic environment is. The humanistic workplace environment is a working condition in which employees function and are treated as human beings. What does it mean? In this environment, they can develop themselves to their full potentials by allowing freedom and autonomy to do their responsibilities based on what they know best. The employees are given the chance to participate in the decision making to determine the direction of the organization. Motivating employees to do their best means giving attention to their personal needs and values and recognizing their contributions (Zsolt, 2014). In line with this concept, Bersin (2014) pointed out further the elements of a humanistic environment such as meaningful work, great leadership, growth opportunities, inclusive, flexible and fun environment, and trusted leadership. Meaningful work can only be attained when employees are given autonomy in conducting their work without being dictated by the management what to do. Besides autonomy, a good humanistic workplace is characterized by great leadership. A great leader is the one who coaches and gives feedbacks to employees and provides development opportunities. Another aspect of a humanistic environment is growth opportunities in the sense that employees are not stagnant in their career but always updated with the new skills related to their work. Second from the last elements of humanistic management is inclusivity, flexibility, and a fun environment. This humanistic environment is characterized by equal opportunity for all without discrimination, allowing a certain amount of flexibility without being so rigid in following the rules and making the environment an exciting workplace to stay. Lastly is the trusted leader in which leaders are trusted by their employees. By practising those elements, the workplace can be a great experience where the employees love to dedicate their life. In other words, the workplace must be a happy place for employees where employees experience happiness and excitement because their needs and values are met (Wagner, 2018).

Those humanistic environment elements are the product of the humanistic management approach. The humanistic management approach is people-oriented management in which it

places a prime priority to fulfil human needs and values to achieve organizational objectives or profits (Mele, 2016). The people-oriented management principle is based on the belief that by giving attention to human needs and values, the objective of the organization will be achieved. Beyond such a purpose, another purpose of humanistic management is to restore human dignity in the workplace as it has been destroyed by bureaucratic and scientific management (Zawadzki, 2018). Bureaucratic management has been accused of turning human beings into machines because there is no flexibility, freedom, and autonomy (Shafritz & Whitbeck, 1981, cited by Akindele, 2016). Thus, humanistic management styles were a great alternative to break the monotonous task created by the bureaucratic management of Max Weber and the scientific management of Taylor to improve productivity and to achieve organizational goals. Humanistic management brought back human beings as a centre of management which was neglected by bureaucratic and scientific management styles and started to focus on human motivation which is centred on human needs and values (Swart, 1973), and focused on improving human relationships in the organization (Murray, 2020). This new management considered the human relationship in the organization as an important element to reach organizational success (Murray, 2020). Besides the relationship, the new management focuses on motivation, work satisfaction, and productivity (Swart, 1973). Motivating employees is not just by giving them rules, procedures but by giving them what they need and value and by giving them more responsibilities and enriching their existing jobs (Herzberg, 1968).

There have studies on the effect of Humanistic management, humanistic environment, and work performance and these studies have pointed out the correlation between humanistic management, humanistic work environment and work performance, job satisfaction, and retention such as Daley (1986), McDaniel (2020), Fitzsimons (2012), Arnaud, and Wasieleski, (2013). Willis Towers Watson (2019) surveyed workplace dignity and the survey found that 95% of employers recognized that a culture of dignity is an important driver of employees' well-being. These studies and surveys are enough bases for management to give serious attention to giving importance to create a humanistic workplace environment to inspire employees to perform and engage in their work (Bersin, 2014). There is a clear negative consequence when management fails to give attention to reinstating human dignity in the workplace (Zawadzki, 2018, Bal, 2017). Reinstating human dignity in the workplace means that management should not prioritize more on rules, regulations, obedience to the authority to achieve organizational goals but prioritize the needs of human beings because management is about people management and it must be people first and people should be treated as human beings with dignity and not machines (Valcour, 2014). Treating human beings with dignity means that employers should not take advantage of the employer-employee relationship and employee's vulnerability (Valcour, 2014). In line with this concept, solon (2018) argued that respect, dignity, and kindness are the foundational principles of the workplace. This is a particular challenge for the management to build a culture of dignity in the workplace (Caprino, 2018), and failing to establish such a culture can destroy a working relationship and employee's performance (Hicks, 2018, cited by Caprino, 2018, Edmons, 2015). Thus, Hicks as cited by Caprion (2018) recommends the management to instil within the workplace a dignity consciousness through organizational policies.

One of the striking characteristics of the humanistic environment is the caring relationship between management and employees (Xesha, 2014). The caring relationship starts with the recognition of employees' contributions to the organization. Thus, the concern of the management is to meet the employees' needs and align employee's values with the organizational values to make the workplace a happy place for everyone. A management

approach is a humanistic approach in which management considers employees' needs, values, and emotions first before making any decision.

Entrepreneurial Environment

We can only understand the meaning of the entrepreneurial environment if we first understand the meaning of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship. Merriam-Webster dictionary defines “entrepreneur” as the “one who organizes, manages, and assumes the risk of a business or enterprise”. One characteristic of an entrepreneur emanated from this definition is risk-taking capability. However, relying on this definition alone, one cannot get a complete picture of the meaning of an entrepreneur. One can get the complete picture of an entrepreneur from Schumpeter (1934) and Kirzner (1973). They had presented the complete meaning of the entrepreneur. For them, entrepreneurs are the bearers of uncertainty and who are not afraid of taking the risk. They are the people who can see ahead of opportunities and consequently can create innovation (Shockley, & Frank, 2011). In line with such a view, Kirzner (1973) considers entrepreneurs as people who are alert to what is going on in the environment particularly the opportunities which lead them to discover new things to satisfy human needs and for a profit (Lai-Yu, 1999). Based on their concept, now we have an idea about the meaning of an entrepreneur that he/she is the one who can face uncertainty, take the risk, and drive innovation. They are the people who have the spirit of freedom and creativity and by having such spirit, they can see new business opportunities and establish a business that consequently leads to economic growth (Petraakis & Kafka, 2016).

The above concepts including the concepts that are offered by Schumpeter (1934) and Kirzner (1973) can be classified under the psychological theory definition of who an entrepreneur is. Under the personality trait theory, an entrepreneur is someone who has the locus of control (Rotter, 1966) and who has a need for achievement (McClelland, 1961). Firstly, he/she believes himself/herself that he/she is the one who controls life's events, not external forces. Studies have found that a successful entrepreneur is associated with those who have an internal locus of control (Bonnett & Furnham, 1991). Besides having the power of locus of control, an entrepreneur is also driven by his/her need for achievement. He/she has an inner desire to achieve something in his life and the need to excel in his/her life. It has also been found by the study that the need for achievement is associated with the entrepreneurs (Shaver & Scott, 1991). However, relying on psychological definition alone may not be enough to capture the whole meaning of an entrepreneur. Such a psychological definition may not be complete without considering the sociological definition of an entrepreneur. Thus, from sociological theory, “an entrepreneur” is the one who knows how to build a social relationship with wider networks and being able to maintain the trust relationship and not taking advantage of others (Reynolds, 1991). Beyond that, under sociological theory, an entrepreneur is the one who is alert to the social condition of life and is willing to do something meaningful with their life and society. Concerning the alertness character, opportunity – based theory defines an entrepreneur as someone who responds to the opportunities offered by the environment and exploits the opportunities to create something (Fiet, 2002). These are people who have always the solution to the problems they see in society (Drucker, 1995). From the concept of entrepreneur, then one can understand the meaning of entrepreneurship. It refers to the effort of establishing a business to attain profit by taking the risk. People go into business because of the business opportunities offered by the market and because they want to have control over their own life (Entrepreneur Handbook, n.d).

From the definition of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship, one can understand the concept of an entrepreneurial environment. Entrepreneurial environment refers to the

psychological definition of an entrepreneur (Rotter, 1966) and also refers to the opportunity – based theory (Fiet, 2002). Based on psychological theory, an entrepreneurial environment is about a workplace where employees are allowed to control their work to achieve what they want to achieve in their work and exercise freedom and autonomy in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. It is an environment in which the employees are not afraid of taking risks and committing mistakes in venturing new ways of doing things to achieve organizational objectives (Chadha, 2020). In this environment, employees are recognized and rewarded when they propose innovations to solve existing problems and are allowed to venture different strategies to perform their jobs (Langer, et.al. 2019). In short, one can get a full summary of the entrepreneurial environment from Hadzima's (2005) seven characteristics of entrepreneurial employees. The first characteristic of an entrepreneurial employee is the ability to deal with risk. This capability will be flourishing and growing when the work environment allows the employee to take the risk. The second characteristic is result-oriented. Again, a result-oriented requires the organization not to impose so many rules and procedures on getting things done but what is important is the result. The organization should allow the employees to define their ways on how to get the result done. The third characteristic is energy and enthusiasm. In this case, motivation is important and the organization should provide the necessary means to sustain the energy of employees to perform their tasks and not burden the employees with so many rules and procedures. The fourth characteristic is the growth potential. Related to this characteristic, the organization should provide employees with the opportunity to go higher in their careers. There must be chances given to all employees to be promoted. The fifth characteristic is a team player. This feature is related to the sociological definition of an entrepreneur. This characteristic requires the organization to build teamwork and maintain a harmonious working relationship. The sixth characteristic is multitasking ability. In this case, the organization should train its employees by giving them more than one responsibility and avoid routines. The seventh characteristic is improvement-oriented. The employees in this case are encouraged to challenge the status quo and are encouraged to propose new solutions or new ways of doing their task. Thus, there should be no control from the management and there is no monopoly of knowledge.

Workplace environment and performance

Organizational performance is not just the product of financial capital but is the product of employees' work engagement. Work engagement is the result of different factors of work attitude such as knowledge, affective, and conative (Abun, et.al. 2020). However, work engagement is also the result of the work environment. The workplace environment is the foundational principle that strengthens and promotes the growth of an organization. The workplace environment is a broad concept that includes the physical and psychological setting of the workplace. It is not only about the physical setup of an office but it is also about what relationship and emotion that employees experience in the workplace (Briner, 2000). The workplace environment must be conducive to which the employees can engage in their work. Earlier times public management was dominated by bureaucratic management, however in the course of its development, bureaucratic management affects negatively job satisfaction, and turnover increases, and thus, such a situation demanded a change in management. Entrepreneurial management came in to solve the problems to introduce another kind of management that emphasized autonomy, creativity, flexibility, output-oriented, and risk-taking. The presence of entrepreneurial management practices changed the situation and consequently, job satisfaction was restored (Langer, et.al, 2019). Such positive development pointed out the

fact that the work environment cannot be undermined by the management if the organization desires to achieve its objective (Langer, et.al. 2019).

Studies have been done to help us understand the influence of the workplace environment on job satisfaction. Early studies have given us some results on the influence of bureaucratic environment and work outcomes. The study of Adler & Borys, (1996) had given us a mixed result. On one hand, a bureaucratic form of governance which is characterized by routines and centralization can form attitudinal outcome in the workplace. In other words, it can change the attitude of employees. On the other hand, a coercive bureaucratic form of governance can also kill creativity and diminish job satisfaction. When the job satisfaction of those who were working in the bureaucratic environment which was characterized by centralization of decision making and doing the same job, in the same way, every day, compared with the job satisfaction of those who were working in an entrepreneurial environment which was characterized by autonomy, and flexibility, the result showed that employees working under coercive bureaucratic management were less satisfied compared to those who are working under entrepreneurial environment (Adler & Borys, 1996). Studies also had shown that when autonomy is diminished, then the perception of independence in decision making is reduced, and consequently, the feeling of self-efficacy is also diminished (Langfred & Moye, 2004, Wood & Bandura, 1989)). When autonomy is stripped from the employees, then job dissatisfaction increases (Cantarelli et al., 2016). Lack of autonomy affects the self-perception of employees and the self-efficacy of employees to perform their job as pointed out by Oyewole and Popoola (2013). Oyewole and Popoola (2013) studied psychological factors such as self-concept, self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and job stress and job performance and their study proved that self-concept, job satisfaction, and job stress affect work performance. Therefore, autonomy working environment must be conducive. The study of Saidi, et.al (2019) supports such finding that there is a correlation between autonomy working environment and job performance. Thus, the management must create a working environment that helps the need for individual autonomy to grow (Ryan and Deci, 2000).

Work engagement

Topic about work engagement is not something new because the term and the concept have been used by many people and many researchers. However, finding a common definition of work engagement never happened and much more on finding the common variables to measure work engagement is not easy (Schaufeli, 2013, Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000) defined work engagement as a positive mental state of mind. Their definition views work engagement from the cognitive aspect of the engagement which means that when a person engaged in his/her work, he/she is fully immersed, focused, and involved mentally in the work. Kahn (1990) defined work engagement in terms of behaviour. Engaged employees are those who "bring in or leave out their selves during work role performance" (p. 694). This definition sees work engagement from the conative aspect of work engagement. While Harter, et.al. (2002) defined work engagement as an employee's emotional connection to the work. This definition sees work engagement from its affective dimension. Many other definitions can be added to the line such as Allport (1945) who viewed work engagement as involvement in the work. Thomas & Velthouse, (1990) considered work engagement as empowerment.

These different definitions confuse what to measure related to work engagement. This is the main reason why many researchers are coming out with their dimensions or variables measuring work engagement. Many researchers have gone into research measuring work engagement from their perspective. Often time work engagement is measured as a single construct as a physical involvement (Kahn, 1990, Allport, 1945) or as an emotional connection

to the work (Harter, et.al., 2002) or mental state of mind in which employees are immersed and focused in their work mentally (Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Focusing on one dimension of work engagement cannot measure the whole concept of work engagement. For example, measuring the emotional aspect only does not represent the concept of work engagement, or measuring its mental dimension does not also represent the whole understanding of work engagement. Kuok and Taormina (2017) had argued that work engagement is not a single construct ((Maslach & Leiter, 1997) but a multidimensional construct.

Based on the components offered by different researchers, Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma & Bakker, (2002) define work engagement as a mental, emotional connection, and physical involvement of employees toward their work. The work engagement involves three dimensions and these are the cognitive, affective, and conative dimensions of the engagement. An employee is engaged in his/her work meaning he/she is immersed, focused, connected mentally, and emotionally to the work, and involved physically in the work. Physical involvement always depends on the cognitive and affective attitude of employees toward the work (Ajzen, 1993). The cognitive and affective aspects of the employees translate into the physical involvement of employees to the work and physical involvement is crucially important because it measures what one knows and feels about the work. It is not enough that employees are immersed mentally and have an emotional attachment to their work without physical involvement because it is only through physical involvement the organizational goal can be achieved (Abun, 2020). Knowledge and emotions toward the work can only be meaningful if it produces work performance.

Source: Langer, et.al. (2019) and Kuok and Taormina (2017).

Figure 1. The conceptual framework reflects the independent and dependent variables of the study. Independent variables are variables that influence the dependent variables (National Library of Medicine, n.d). The figure reflects the influence of the work environment on the work engagement of employees. Any change in the work environment can cause a change in the work engagement of employees.

Statement of the Problems

The study wanted to determine the influence of the work environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and the work engagement of employees. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the work environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:
 - a. Bureaucratic environment
 - b. Humanistic Environment
 - c. Entrepreneurial environment
2. What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:
 - a. Cognitive engagement
 - b. Affective engagement
 - c. Conative engagement?
3. Is there a relationship between the work environment and the work engagement of employees?

Assumptions

The study assumes that the work environment can affect the work engagement of employees and both can be measured. It also assumes that the questionnaires are valid and the answers to those questions are objective.

Hypothesis

Langer, et.al. (2019) have argued that a bureaucratic work environment affects the job satisfaction of employees. The current study also hypothesizes that bureaucratic, humanistic, and entrepreneurial work environment affect the work engagement of employees.

Scope, Delimitation, and limitation of the Study

The scope of the study is the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. Ilocos Region has two provinces which are Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte. It delimits its investigation on the three work environments namely bureaucratic, humanistic, and entrepreneurial work environment and works engagement in terms of the cognitive, affective, and conative work environment. The study is limited because it does not cover the whole Divine Word Colleges in Northern Luzon and only measures limited variables of the work environment.

III. Research Methodology

The research methodology involves procedures, techniques that are used to carry out the study scientifically. The research methodology determines the quality and reliability of the study (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). Thus, the study was carried out through appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Since the study is quantitative research and it used descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of the work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and its effect on the work engagement of employees. The use of descriptive research is to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and tabulated through statistical methods. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency

distribution, describe characteristics of people, situation, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes “what is” about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

In line with the current study, the descriptive assessment and correlational method were deployed. The study determines the level of the work environment and its effect on work engagement. This was to determine what the dominant work environment of Divine word Colleges is and to what extent it affects the work engagement of employees.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte and these schools are located in Vigan City and Laoag City.

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees and faculty of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The total enumeration sampling was used and 206 faculty and employees were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires of the work environment of Langer, et.al. (2019) and the questionnaires of Kuok and Taormina (2017) on the work engagement inventory with three 6-items subscales.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the President of the Colleges, requesting them to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college. The researcher personally met the Presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires.

The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the college.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In consistence with the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design, therefore descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of the different work environments and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of different work environments toward the work engagement of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very high</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

IV. Data Presentation and Analysis

As scientific research, data are very important. This part presents the data that was gathered through research questionnaires. The data presentations are arranged according to the structure of the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the work environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:

- a. *Bureaucratic environment*
- b. *Humanistic Environment*
- c. *Entrepreneurial environment*

Table 1. The Work Environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Bureaucratic Work Environment

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Employees are always doing the same job and the same way every day	3.76	A
2. All employees must follow the established rules and procedures.	4.09	A
3. There is little action taken until a supervisor or the higher up approves a decision.	3.77	A
4. Even small matters have to be referred to someone higher up for the final answer.	3.74	A
5. In general, a person who wants to make his/her own decisions would be quickly discouraged.	3.51	A
6. Employees are working under close monitoring of their supervisor.	3.82	A
7. One cannot do his/her job in his/her way but he/she has to follow the rules and procedures.	3.75	A
8. Communications, decisions, and proceedings are put in writing for future references.	3.91	A
9. Employees are afraid of violating the rules because it means punishment.	3.60	A
Composite Mean	3.77	A

Source: Langer, et.al. (2019)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

As reflected on the data, it shows that as a whole, the bureaucratic work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region gained a composite mean of 3.77 which is interpreted as "agree or high". This result implies that the bureaucratic work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even when the items are taken separately, they all are evaluated within the same level mean ranges with the interpretation of "agree or high" such as "doing the same job and the same way every day (3.76), following the established rules and procedures (4.06), there is little action taken until a supervisor or the higher up approves a decision (3.77), even small matters have to be referred to someone higher up for final answer (3.74), a person who wants to make his/her own decisions would be quickly discouraged (3.51), employees are working under close monitoring of their supervisor (3.82), one cannot do his/her job in his/her way but he/she has to follow the rules and procedures (3.75), communications, decisions, and proceedings are put in writing for future references (3.91), employees are afraid of violating the rules because it means punishment" (3.60). The finding indicates that the environment is highly bureaucratic which refers to how the administrators manage the institution. Bureaucratic management has been criticized because of its effect on autonomy and freedom, therefore, a

high mean rating on the bureaucratic environment means that these are the areas of management that need to be fixed or improved.

Table 2. The Work Environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Humanistic Environment

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. The management considers the ideas of employees when making decisions.	3.48	A
2. The management always tries its best to serve the needs of employees.	3.46	A
3. The management listens to the employees when the employees counter problems in their work.	3.41	A
4. The management respect and treat the employees as human beings with dignity.	3.44	A
5. The management recognizes the good effort of the employees to help the institution.	3.42	A
6. There is open communication between employees and management.	3.38	SWA
7. When making decisions, the management always consider the effect of the decision on the employees.	3.29	SWA
8. The management prioritizes the employees' condition first before work.	3.22	SWA
Composite Mean	3.39	SWA

Source: Langer, et.al. (2019)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very high</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/ High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/ Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/ Very Low</i>

Looking at the data on the table, it reveals that as a whole, the work environment, in terms of humanistic work environment obtained a composite mean of 3.39 which is described as "somewhat agree or moderate". This output indicates that the humanistic work environment of the Divine Word Colleges is not very high or high and it is also not very low or low but it is a moderate level. However, when taking them separately, it appears that not all items are rated within the same level mean range with the interpretation of "somewhat agree/moderate or agree or high". On one hand, the following items are rated with the description of "agree or high" such as "the management considers the ideas of employees when making decisions (3.48), the management always tries their best to serve the needs of employees (3.46), the management listens to the employees when the employees counter problems in their work (3.41), the management respect and treat the employees as human beings with dignity (3.44), the management recognizes the good effort of the employees to help the institution' (3.42). On the other hand, the following items were rated "somewhat agree or moderate" such as "there is open communication between employees and management (3.38), when making decisions, the management always consider the effect of the decision on the employees (3.29), and the management prioritizes the employees' condition first before the work" (3.22). The lower mean rating suggests that these are the areas of improvement along with the humanistic management practice of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region.

Table 3. The Work Environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Entrepreneurial Work Environment

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Employees are encouraged to take the risk.	3.34	SWA
2. Employees in this organization are rewarded for developing innovative solutions.	3.29	SWA
3. This organization has a strong commitment to innovation.	3.39	SWA
4. People who develop innovative solutions to problems are rewarded.	3.20	SWA
5. This institution is a very dynamic and entrepreneurial place. People are willing to stick their necks out and take risks.	3.19	SWA
6. Employees are free to perform their work in their way to achieve the result.	3.40	SWA
7. The institution is result-oriented and not process-oriented.	3.39	SWA
Composite Mean	3.31	SWA

Source: Langer, et.al. (2019)

Legend

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/ Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Based on the data presented in the table, it manifests that as a whole, the work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in terms of entrepreneurial work environment obtained a composite mean rating of 3.31 which is described as "somewhat agree or moderate". These composite means suggests that the entrepreneurial work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high or high and it is also not very low or low but to a moderate extent. Even if the items are taken singly, all of the items fall within the mean range with the interpretation of "somewhat agree or moderate" such as "employees are encouraged to take a risk (3.34) and are rewarded for developing innovative solutions (3.29), the organization has a strong commitment to innovation(3.39), people who develop innovative solutions to problems are rewarded (3.20), and this institution is a very dynamic and entrepreneurial place and are willing to stick their necks out and take risks (3.19). There are only two items that were rated "agree or high" such as "employees are free to perform their work in their way to achieve the result (3.40) and the institution is the result-oriented and not process-oriented" (3.39).

This lower mean rating indicates that as whole management has not been exerting very high or high effort in encouraging entrepreneurial spirit within the employees. This is considered a problem that needs to be addressed by the management. The entrepreneurial spirit is important to be cultivated to create an innovative and competitive environment.

Table 4. Summary of Work Environment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region

ITEMS	Mean	DR
I. Bureaucratic Work Environment	3.77	A
II. Humanistic Management Style	3.39	SWA
III. Entrepreneurial Work Environment	3.31	SWA
Overall Mean	3.49	A

Legend

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

The data on the summary table demonstrates that as a whole the work environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region obtained a composite mean of 3.49 which interpreted as "agree or high". This result does not indicate a positive environment because the dominant environment is the bureaucratic environment (3.77) which has been criticized to be negative, while the other two dimensions of the environment such as humanistic and entrepreneurial environment are lower with a lower weighted mean of 3.39 and 3.31. The result suggests that the working environment of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is dominated by the bureaucratic working environment which may not be good for the development and competitiveness of the institution. The management needs to balance the bureaucratic environment with the different working environment dimensions.

Problem 2: What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:

- a. *Cognitive engagement*
- b. *Affective engagement*
- c. *Conative engagement?*

Table 5. The Work Engagement of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Cognitive Engagement

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work.	3.90	A
2. Wherever I am, things happen that often remind me of my work.	3.86	A
3. My mind is fully engaged with my work.	3.99	A
4. I rarely think about a time when I am working.	3.81	A
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work.	3.94	A
6. I give a lot of mental attention to my work.	4.01	A
Composite Mean	3.92	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Looking at the data on the table, it displays that as a whole, the work engagement of employees in terms of cognitive engagement gained a composite mean rating of 3.92 which is described as "agree or high". This composite mean implies that the work engagement of employees in terms of their cognitive engagement is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even if the items are taken singly, they all were rated within the same level of mean rating with the description of "agree or high" such as "my mind is often full

of ideas about my work (3.90), wherever I am, things happen that often remind me of my work (3.86), my mind is fully engaged with my work (3.99), I rarely think about a time when I am working (3.81), my thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work (3.94), and I give a lot of mental attention to my work” (4.01).

Though the mean rating is not very high but high, however, it indicates that employees are highly engaged in their work. Highly engaged employees are necessary for the attainment of the goals of the institution and therefore, the management needs to strengthen and maintain the work engagement of employees by improving the work environment.

Table 6. The Work Engagement of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Emotional Work Engagement

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.	3.75	A
2. I am very eager to do my work.	3.87	A
3. I feel very happy when I am carrying out my responsibilities at work.	3.83	A
4. I feel very good about the work that I do.	3.82	A
5. I feel strong enthusiasm for my work.	3.83	A
6. I feel a sense of gratification with my work performance.	3.83	A
Composite Mean	3.82	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

As pointed out by the data on the table, it displays that as a whole, the work engagement of employees in terms of emotional work engagement obtained a composite mean of 3.82 which is described or interpreted as “agree or high”. This mean rating indicates that the work engagement of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even when the items are taken separately, they all were rated within the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of “agree or high” such as “I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working (3.75), I am very eager to do my work (3.87), I feel very happy when I am carrying out my responsibilities at work (3.83), I feel very good about the work that I do (3.82), I feel strong enthusiasm for my work (3.83), and I feel a sense of gratification with my work performance” (3.83).

The composite mean of 3.82 suggests that employees are highly engaged in their work in terms of emotional engagement. It demonstrates that employees are highly engaged mentally and emotionally in their work. Such an environment needs to be maintained or even improved to attain the organizational goals.

Table 7. The Work Engagement of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Physical Work Engagement

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. No matter how much I work, I have a high level of energy.	3.81	A
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work.	3.84	A

3. I always have a lot of energy for my work.	3.80	A
4. I am often physically driven by my work.	3.86	A
5. I am frequently energized by my work.	3.85	A
6. I find my work to be physically invigorating.	3.77	A
Composite Mean	3.82	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Lastly, along with the work engagement, the data reveals that as a whole, the work engagement of employees in terms of physical engagement received a composite mean rating of 3.82 which is translated as “agree or high”. This result points out that employees’ physical engagement is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even if the items are taken separately, all items were rated within the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of “agree or high” such as “no matter how much I work, I have a high level of energy (3.81), I have a great deal of stamina for my work (3.84), I always have a lot of energy for my work (3.80), I am often physically driven by my work (3.86), I am frequently energized by my work (3.85), and I find my work to be physically invigorating” (3.77).

This result (3.82) suggests that employees are highly engaged in their work physically. High physical engagement is important because employees need to carry out their work by being present in their work and engaged directly in their work. Therefore, the employees need to have energy, and stamina to engage in their work.

Table 8. Summary of Work Engagement of Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
I. Cognitive Work Engagement	3.92	A
II. Emotional Work Engagement	3.82	A
III. Physical Work Engagement	3.82	A
Overall Mean	3.85	A

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low</i>

The summary table indicates that overall, employees’ work engagement obtained an overall mean rating of 3.85 which is described as “agree or high”. This implies that overall the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even if the dimensions are taken singly, they all were rated within the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of “agree or high” such as cognitive work engagement (3.92), emotional work engagement (3.82) and

physical work engagement (3.82). This result indicates that employees are highly engaged in their work.

Though this result suggests a high engagement, however, it needs still to be improved to be very highly engaged in their work. The institutions can only achieve their goals by the employees who are highly engaged in their work. This can be done by improving the work environment.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between the work environment and the work engagement of employees?

Table 9. Relationship between Work Environment and Work Engagement

		Cognitive Work Engagement	Emotional Work Engagement	Physical Work Engagement
Bureaucratic Work Environment	Pearson Correlation	.360**	.159*	.305**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.023	.000
	N	206	206	206
Humanistic Management Style	Pearson Correlation	.399**	.379**	.487**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206
Entrepreneurial Work Environment	Pearson Correlation	.442**	.364**	.481**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table on the work environment and work engagement show that there is a significant correlation between work environment and work engagement. The correlation table demonstrates that the bureaucratic environment is correlated significantly at 0.01 level (2-tailed) with the cognitive work engagement, with the emotional work engagement at 0.05 level (2-tailed) and with physical work engagement at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The humanistic work environment is also correlated significantly with the cognitive work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed), with the emotional work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed) and with physical work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed). Lastly, entrepreneurial work engagement is also correlated significantly with the cognitive work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed), with the emotional work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed) and with the physical work engagement at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table suggests that improving the work engagement of employees is necessary to improve the work environment with its three dimensions. Positive changes in the work environment will improve the work engagement of employees.

Result and Analysis

Based on the result of the study, it shows that when the bureaucratic environment is playing dominant in a workplace, the tendency is the humanistic and entrepreneurial environment is diminishing or not growing. This finding is consistent with the criticism of the negative effect of bureaucracy. It has been accused of using people as machine as pointed out

by Ronald (2010) that bureaucracy overpowers reason and cause people to pursue worthless goals and endeavours. Despite of its strength in promoting efficiency, studies have been done along with the negative effect of bureaucratic environment, or bureaucratic leadership. Wahab and Jiwando (2008) pointed out that when bureaucratic management prevails over humanistic and entrepreneurial management, employees lose their discretionary power in decision making. This finding is also strengthened by Hirst, et.al. (2011) that the negative effect of bureaucracy is the loss of creativity and innovation. The result of this study calls the management to balance the management approach which is not only dominated by bureaucratic style but should be combined with the humanistic and entrepreneurial approach in managing the institutions.

However, as we see in the result of the work engagement, it shows that the work engagement of employees is high but not very high. This indicates that despite the bureaucratic environment, or bureaucratic leadership style, employees are still engaging their job cognitively, emotionally and physically. This can be the result of strict monitoring and compliance to the rules and the imposition of punishment when the employees are not coming out with the expected output. Therefore, despite the criticism of the negative consequence of bureaucratic leadership, it is still the one that produces output.

Based on the result of the correlation, the study found a correlation between work environment particularly bureaucratic, humanistic and entrepreneurial environment and work engagement. It just means that solving work engagement is necessarily changing or improving the work environment. In other words, when bureaucratic management is balanced with humanistic and entrepreneurial management, the work engagement of employees can be very high and is not just high.

The output of this study contributes to the wider discussion of the elements of the work environment that are necessary to improve the work engagement and performance of employees. It is high time to call on the management to humanize the bureaucracy and allows the entrepreneurial spirit of employees to promote innovation and competitiveness. Failing to humanize the bureaucracy, the employees will always be seen as a machine under the control of management.

Conclusion

The objective of the study was to determine the level of work environment concerning the three dimensions: bureaucratic, humanistic and entrepreneurial environment and how it affects the work engagement of employees. The study found that the bureaucratic environment is high but not very high, and the humanistic and entrepreneurial environment are moderate. About the work engagement, it was found that it is high in the three dimensions as cognitive, affective and physical engagement. When it comes to the correlation between the two variables, work environment and work engagement are correlated. Even the individual dimensions of the work environment are significantly correlated to the different dimensions of work engagement. It just suggests that the management needs to improve and balance the bureaucratic management style with humanistic and entrepreneurial management style to improve the work engagement of employees to a very high level of engagement. Therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

The output of this study contributes to a complex discussion on the bureaucratic, humanistic and entrepreneurial leadership specifically the relevance of bureaucratic leadership style without the balance of humanistic and entrepreneurial leadership style. There is a need to humanize the organization with the right combination of bureaucratic, humanistic and entrepreneurial leadership styles. The study also recognizes its limitation, particularly its

coverage and there is a need to widen the scope of the study to get the precise picture of the effect of work environment and work engagement.

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